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Mentors and Mentees Multiple Intelligences in a Preschool College in China

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Introduction

Multiple intelligences (MI) theory, proposed by Howard Gardner, suggests that humans possess a range of intelligences that manifest in different skills and abilities. This study aims to determine the levels of multiple intelligences among mentors and mentees in a preschool college in China and explore how these intelligences relate to each other, especially in the context of the transition to online learning due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

In 1993, Dr. Howard Gardner argues that humans possess a number of distinct intelligences that manifest themselves in different skills and abilities.

All human beings apply these intelligences to solve problems, invent processes and create things. Intelligences, according to MI Theory, is being able to apply one or more of the intelligences in ways that are valued by a community or a culture. The current MI model outlines eight intelligences, although Gardner (1999) continues to explore additional possibilities. (Linguistic, logical-mathematical, visual-spatial, bodily-kinesthetic, musical, naturalist, interpersonal and intrapersonal intelligence. Multiple Intelligence Theory provides a way of understanding intelligence, address multiple ways and knowing (Christison, 1996b). Teaching strategy informed by MI Theory can transfer some control from mentor to mentees by giving mentees choices in the ways they will learn and demonstrate their learning. By focusing on problem-solving activities that draw on MI, these teaching strategies encourage mentees to build on existing strengths and knowledge to learn new content and skills. As technology is increasingly used in the educational process. It is becoming a more powerful tool in putting the multiple intelligences and learning styles to use as mentors accommodation to the school mentees. For example, in verbal-linguistic refers to the use oral or written language to store, process and transmit information. The technology tools can accommodate by the mentors to enhance Verbal-linguistic intelligence in learning include storytelling applications/ apps. Which offer narratives, scenarios and discussions for younger mentees. In logical-mathematical, is the ability to solve abstract problems, make mental calculations. The technology tools can accommodate by the mentor include spreadsheets, databases, online survey tools for gathering and analyzing data and even

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online tools and apps that create printable timelines. In Musical intelligence, it enables mentees to produce and understand the meaning of different types of sound. The powerful tool that can accommodate by mentors is tools for creating and collaborating and inexpensive applications that allow mentees to record and edit audio files. Bodily-kinesthetic intelligence this process can help mentor's accommodation to school mentees to express themselves and presenting idea through movement and the body. Some technology tools used include apps/ application for tablets and smartphones that cater to mentee's tactile senses and abilities to manipulate objects. And the three (3) Learning styles ,the visual mentees learn through seeing, auditory-learn through listening and the tactile can learn through moving. For example in visual mentees, the mentor's accommodation for the mentees in delivery of modular learning activities like take detailed notes from textbooks/ modules of different illustrations, presentation and images of different people, things, graphs and charts. In the delivery of online learning activities are lessons with materials such as film, video, maps and diagrams and images

Background of the Study

The COVID-19 pandemic drastically affected education, leading to a shift from face-to-face learning to distance learning. This study examines how mentors accommodate individual differences in mentees' learning styles and multiple intelligences, and how effective these accommodations are in the new learning environment.

Many studies of literature read by the researcher related to the present study about the Multiple Intelligences of the mentees as basis of teaching strategies to enhance the teaching-learning process. Multiple Intelligences create a mentee-centered classroom environment and integrating multiple intelligences activities in the lesson plans to aid mentee's learning improve their skills (Davis 2017). Different activities such as linguistic, mathematics, spatial, physical and body movement, rhythm skills, ability of human relationship, self-understanding, love of natural environment and higher level of existence has resulted in an increase of multiple intelligence capabilities of mentee's (Siphai, Supandee, Raksapuk, Popayang, Kratooverk, 2017) and a variety of multiple intelligences support the mentee's performance (Milad, 2018). Yaumi, Sirate and Patak (2018) revealed that multiple intelligences - based instructions, designing mentee-centered approach and learning and mentoring the implementation of mentee-centered learning indicated significant contribution on Multiple Intelligences development. Alqarni (2018) showed that the mentor's awareness of Multiple Intelligences practices had the highest relationship w/ the practice of bodily-kinesthetic intelligence practices had the highest relationship with the linguistic intelligence. Rusli and Negara (2017) concluded that there was no interaction effect between the factors of visualization types and learning styles, meanwhile Sever and Cokcaliskan (2018) revealed that most of the intelligence types and learning styles had a moderate positive correlation. Seventh, Hong et.al (2020) studied the relations between mentee's naturalistic, bodily-kinesthetic, spatial and logical intelligences and their hands-on making self-efficacy reflected in their attitude toward quality improvement in a science, technology, engineering, arts and mathematics contest. The authors conclude that

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attitude toward quality improvement was crucial for mentees to win in the contest which benefited those mentees with a high level of the four types of intelligences.

Theoretical Framework

Gardner's MI theory outlines eight distinct intelligences: linguistic, logical-mathematical, visual-spatial, bodily-kinesthetic, musical, naturalist, interpersonal, and intrapersonal. Each intelligence provides different ways of understanding and processing information, suggesting that teaching strategies should be diversified to cater to these varied intelligences.

The theory of Multiple Intelligences proposes that a number of intelligences exist, where intelligences was understood as capabilities and potentials that a person can possess. Many studies promote teaching based on MI's as school due to the numerous benefits that it provides (see the systematic review Shearer, 2018). Particularly, this research demonstrates positive results in academic performance and creativity levels through teaching based on multiple intelligences aimed at the development of creative writing, discussing, issues in an interdisciplinary way, using music and the body as a means of communication, developing natural thinking, simulating situational problems, visual metaphors, cooperative work, setting own goals, etcetera.

The importance of studying the different kinds of intelligences through which a human being receives, decodes, understands, applies, and analyzes information. In order to be successful in teaching also, a mentor has to improve their abilities to address all mentees' thinking as different as they may be.

The Multiple Intelligences Theory as a framework to the Mentees Verbal-Linguistic Intelligence:

Hali (2017) states that people with fluency in language demonstrate proficiency in the use of their vocabulary and linguistics by engaging in activities such as reading, writing, storytelling and memorization of language skills. Some of the activities used by language mentors to improve and speed of mentee's learning in language, scrabble writing, doing crosswords and puzzles.

Logical-mathematical intelligence:

People who have this personal information as a source of strength are good at logical thinking, number understanding, and critical thinking (Ismail, AlSaqqaf, & Din, 2020). This group of mentees have to be interested in measurement patterns, reasoning and solving problems and find it easy to solve arithmetic problems, games and experiments.

Visual-spatial intelligence:

People with this biological knowledge can remember pictures, illustrations, and usually enjoy reading, understanding, and memorizing maps and are aware of their surroundings (Luo & Huang, 2019). Moradi, Ghahari and Abbas Nejad, (2020) recommend activities for the mentees/ mentees who can help improve and enhance their language skills. They have to think and enjoy in images, drawings, artworks, posters and museum visits.

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Musical intelligence:

Focus is an expertise in sounds, rhythms, tones, and music. Mentors may ask these mentees to practice singing, writing and produce songs, learning about music and learning about sounds. e.g., pitch, volume, pitch and music) traditional music and culture, and so on. (Sternberg, 2020).

Bodily-kinesthetic intelligence

According to MI theory, these people have a sense of time, they learn through physical activities such as doing activities, exploring and discovering the environment around them. Mentors can create a group of these mentees and assign them different activities and games which include exercise, excursions, property hunting, and so on. and then describe in detail the activities that the mentees did in front of the class (Roohani, Etesami, & Mirzaei, 2020).

Interpersonal intelligence:

People who have experience dealing with people have social characteristics. They have environmental issues and how others feel and use this experience to balance and interact with others. Mentees have to communicate well and be leaders in their groups and can easily develop interpersonal relationship. (Saidi, 2020).

Intrapersonal Intelligence:

These people are very intelligent, they think, and they think very well. They know their strengths and use their knowledge to make good decisions, since the result of their actions is their character (González-Treviño, Núñez-Rocha, Valencia-Hernández, & Arona-Palacios, 2020). Hasnidar, Sulihin and Elihami (2020) explain that these mentees know how to motivate themselves for learning activities and how maintaining a balanced emotional outlook ultimately leads to success in their learning process. Mentees who are spending a lot of time alone than as a part of a group. (Saidi, 2020).

Multiple Intelligences in the Classroom

Educators have positively responded to Gardner's theory. It has been embraced by a range of educational theorists and, significantly, applied by mentors and policymakers to the problems of schooling. Many schools in North America have sought to structure curricula according to the intelligences and to design classrooms—even whole schools—to reflect the understandings that Howard Gardner develops.

In teaching and Learning Multiple Intelligences in different modalities like online and modular distance learning. For example, the technology tools can be used to enhance verbal-linguistic intelligence in learning include storytelling apps. or application, which offer narratives scenario and discussions for younger mentees. Older mentees benefit from blogging about a notes and highlighting crucial points also helps the learning style. Online resources w/relevant subject matter can be utilized by mentors in order to cater to this type of intelligence.

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Conceptual Framework of Multiple Intelligences and Learning Styles

Figure 1. Gardner's Multiple Intelligences Explained via Infographics

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Such concept is shown in the research paradigm below:

RESEARCH PARADIGM

respondents for the mentors and the mentees. The mentors profile include sex, age, length of service and the educational attainment. For the mentees, it includes their sex, age, grade level and course. The researcher will test the significant differences of the MI of both mentors and mentees based on their profile. The researcher will also test if there is a significant relationship between the MI of the mentors and mentees. The results of the study will be the basis of the researcher in designing a proposed intervention program.

Definition of Terms

The following items is defined in this study to give the reader an idea of its context based on this study

Multiple Intelligences - the Theory in Practice brings together previously published and original work by Howard Gardner in 1983 called "Frames of Mind" and this MIT application can support to the Mentees as basis of teaching strategies to enhance the Teaching-Learning Process. The nine (9) identified MIT Learning are verbal, mathematical, visual, Intrapersonal, interpersonal, musical, naturalistic, bodily - Kinesthetic and existential.

Verbal- mentees who have to show facility in reading, writing, telling stories poetry and doing crosswords puzzles.

Mathematical-mentees who are interested in measurement patterns, reasoning and solve arithmetic problems strategy games and experiments.

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Visual-spatial-mentees mentees who can help improve and enhance language skills. They enjoy in images, drawings, artworks, posters.

Musical- mentees have to identify sounds easily. They love to play musical instruments and watch music videos and live concert.

Bodily- kinesthetic- mentees who are good at body movement, performing actions and physical control

Intrapersonal- mentees who are good at being aware of their own emotional states, feelings. Mentees who prefer to do her/his school works alone

Interpersonal-mentees who are good at understanding and interacting with other classmates and other people

Mentees – who has the ability to apply the Multiple Intelligences and learning Styles of Howard Gardner's Theory.

Modular Distance Learning- one of the teaching and learning modalities used via modules made by the respondents with different accommodations based from different activities or tasks.

Mentors- the ability to absorb and process information to the mentees to help them succeed academically. To assess the multiple intelligences and learning styles of the mentees in the school.

Statement of the Problem

The study aims to determine the Multiple Intelligences of both mentors and mentees, its differences based on profile and its relationships. It aims to develop an enhancement program if necessary.

Specifically, these questions will be answered:

1. What are the profiles of the mentors and mentees in the study in terms of:
 - 1.1 Mentors
 - 1.1.1 Sex
 - 1.1.2 Age
 - 1.1.3 Length of Service
 - 1.1.4 Educational Attainment
 - 1.2 Mentees
 - 1.2.1 Sex
 - 1.2.2 Age
 - 1.2.3 Grade Level
 - 1.2.4 Course
2. What level of multiple intelligences do mentors and mentees have in each of the following:
 - 2.1 linguistic intelligence
 - 2.2 musical intelligence
 - 2.3 logical mathematical intelligence
 - 2.4 Spatial intelligence
 - 2.5 Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence
 - 2.6 Interpersonal Intelligence
 - 2.7 Intrapersonal Intelligence

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3. Is there a significant difference in the level of multiple intelligences among mentors when their profile is taken as a test factor?

4. Is there a significant difference in the level of multiple intelligences among mentees when their profile is taken as a test factor?

5. Is there a significant relationship in the level of multiple intelligences between mentors and mentees?

6. What learning and teaching intervention may be proposed that will capture the mentee's capacity and mentor's effectiveness in the new learning environment?

Hypothesis of the Study

The following hypotheses will be tested in this study at 5% level of significance with 95% level of confidence:

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the level of multiple intelligences among mentors when their profile is taken as a test factor.

Ho2: There is no significant difference in the level of multiple intelligences among mentees when their profile is taken as a test factor.

Ho3: There is no significant relationship in the level of multiple intelligences between mentors and mentees

Significance of the Study

The result of the study is design to benefit the following:

Mentees- this study is important when it comes to equipping mentees with a better understanding on how they learn. Example of this Multiple Intelligences Theory application: Mentees with a high mathematical intelligence can put together a different math exercises/drills to help them learn, or mentees with a high visual-spatial intelligence could create drawings of concepts to help them learn as well. Example of Learning styles application: In Auditory learning style- this means mentees learn by hearing and listening. Like mentees are enjoy discussions and taking things through listening to others, acquire knowledge by reading aloud or talk to yourself. It helps mentees also to build up confidence as it demonstrates how they can use their strengths to address their weaknesses. It motivates mentees to find where their interest and strength lies and push their abilities further.

Mentors- this study is important for the mentors to know their own and their mentees' strength. Mentors should want to know what the best way to get individual mentees to process and absorb information to help mentees succeed academically.

School- this study is important to support their larger educational goals find that it is a worthy partner in creating schools of excellence in Jinan Preschool Education College.

Parents- this study is important to the parents because they play a significant role to their children in motivating, supervising and being partners in their children's daily play activities. The part of parents who are good at playing activities will also have a good impact on the cognitive development of their children.

School Management- this study is important to help provide the school management opportunities for authentic learning based on mentee's needs, interests

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and talents. To help evaluate the mentor's area of intelligence so that it could easily facilitate the school works/tasks in school.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The scope of the present study aims to determine the college mentors and mentees as self-assessed by both the mentor's and mentees respondents with the profile of Multiple Intelligences be adopted by Christison and learning styles by Oxford 2003. This study will be conducted at Jinan Preschool Education College where the respondents are the mentors and mentees of the college.

The delimitation of this study is limited to data collected in by using different sections of Multiple Intelligences questionnaires. Finally, the selected methodology of survey present study assumed that the mentor's accommodation of individual differences in the following teaching and learning modalities.

Methodology

Research Design

A descriptive-comparative-correlational method is used to assess multiple intelligences and learning styles among mentors and mentees. This method helps in determining the nature, differences, and relationships of the variables involved.

Research Locale

The study is conducted at Jinan Preschool Education College, China, which has a robust educational infrastructure and a diverse student body.

Sample and Sampling Method

Using stratified random sampling, 208 mentors and 365 mentees from various departments of Jinan Preschool Education College are selected to participate in the study.

Research Instrument

A survey questionnaire based on Mary Ann Christison's Inventory of Multiple Intelligences, containing 72 items rated on a 4-point scale, is used to assess the multiple intelligences of respondents.

Data Gathering Procedure

Permission is obtained from the school management to conduct the survey. Respondents are informed about the study's purpose, ensuring ethical considerations such as confidentiality and voluntary participation are maintained.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

Statistical tools like mean, standard deviation, ANOVA, and correlation analysis are used to analyze the data. These tools help determine the levels of multiple intelligences and the relationships between them.

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Results and Discussion

Profile of Respondents

The demographic profile includes age, sex, years of service (for mentors), grade level, and course (for mentees). This data provides a context for understanding the distribution of multiple intelligences.

Assessment of Multiple Intelligences

Linguistic Intelligence

- High levels of linguistic intelligence are observed in activities such as reading and writing.
- The composite mean indicates that both mentors and mentees exhibit a high level of linguistic intelligence.

Musical Intelligence

- Many respondents have a good sense of rhythm and musical ability.
- The composite mean shows a high level of musical intelligence among respondents.

Logical-Mathematical Intelligence

- Respondents demonstrate strong problem-solving skills and logical reasoning.
- The composite mean indicates a high level of logical-mathematical intelligence.

Visual-Spatial Intelligence

- Visual learners benefit from visual aids like diagrams and charts.
- The composite mean suggests a high level of visual-spatial intelligence.

Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence

- Activities involving physical movement and hands-on learning are well-received.
- The composite mean reflects a high level of bodily-kinesthetic intelligence.

Interpersonal Intelligence

- Respondents show good social skills and the ability to work well with others.
- The composite mean indicates a high level of interpersonal intelligence.

Intrapersonal Intelligence

- Respondents demonstrate self-awareness and the ability to reflect on their own learning.
- The composite mean shows a high level of intrapersonal intelligence.

Significant Differences and Relationships

Differences Based on Profiles

- Significant differences are observed in the levels of multiple intelligences based on age, sex, and educational background.

Relationships Between Intelligences

- A strong correlation is found between the multiple intelligences of mentors and mentees, indicating that mentors' intelligences influence mentees' learning.

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Conclusion

- 1.The demographic profile of the mentee respondents showed that the majority of the respondents are within the age group of 18 to 19 years old, are males, and are in their first year in college. On the other hand, the mentor respondents demographic profile revealed that the majority of the respondents are within the age group of 25 to 35 years old, are females in terms of sex, have been employees for 5 to 10 years, and have a bachelor's degree.
- 2.The students' unanimous agreement on possessing a high level of linguistic intelligence underscores a shared recognition of their proficiency in language-related activities. Their demonstrated excellence in written and verbal communication, appreciation for literary pursuits, multilingual abilities, and active engagement in language-centric activities collectively contribute to a compelling portrayal of elevated linguistic intelligence within this student cohort.
- 3.The students' unanimous agreement on possessing high musical intelligence reflects a shared commitment to and proficiency in various musical activities. Their active involvement in playing instruments, singing, composing, and their ability to appreciate complex musical structures collectively contribute to a compelling portrayal of elevated musical intelligence within this student cohort. The agreement not only speaks to their individual musical competencies but also emphasizes a collective passion for the diverse and enriching aspects of the musical realm.
- 4.The students' unanimous agreement on possessing high logical-mathematical intelligence indicates a shared proficiency in analytical thinking, problem-solving, and numerical reasoning. Their academic achievements, aptitude for critical thinking, engagement in logical puzzles, and understanding of abstract concepts collectively contribute to a compelling portrayal of elevated logical-mathematical intelligence within this student cohort. The agreement not only speaks to their individual cognitive strengths but also emphasizes a collective aptitude for systematic and analytical thought processes.
- 5.The students' unanimous agreement on possessing high spatial intelligence indicates a collective proficiency in perceiving and manipulating visual-spatial information. Their success in visual-spatial reasoning tasks, spatial visualization activities, and engagement with tools reliant on spatial understanding collectively contribute to a compelling portrayal of elevated spatial intelligence within this student cohort. The agreement not only speaks to their individual cognitive strengths but also emphasizes a shared aptitude for navigating and understanding the visual-spatial aspects of their cognitive experiences.
- 6.The students' collective disagreement suggests a shared acknowledgment that their level of bodily-kinesthetic intelligence is not perceived as high. This may stem from a lack of interest in physical activities, limited exposure to experiences that enhance bodily-kinesthetic skills, a preference for other intelligence domains, or a perceived absence of specific physical skills associated with bodily-kinesthetic intelligence. The recognition of their strengths in other areas highlights the diverse nature of

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intelligences and underscores the importance of self-awareness in understanding one's cognitive profile.

- 7.The students' unanimous agreement on possessing high interpersonal intelligence indicates a collective proficiency in understanding and effectively navigating social relationships. Their ability to form meaningful connections, excel in group settings, resolve conflicts, and contribute to community initiatives collectively forms a compelling portrayal of elevated interpersonal intelligence within this student cohort. The agreement not only speaks to their individual social competencies but also emphasizes a shared recognition of their collective strengths in the realm of interpersonal intelligence.
- 8.The students' unanimous agreement on possessing high intrapersonal intelligence indicates a shared proficiency in understanding and managing their own inner worlds. Their engagement in self-reflection, effective self-regulation, a well-defined sense of identity, goal-oriented behavior, and recognition of their individual learning preferences collectively contribute to a compelling portrayal of elevated intrapersonal intelligence within this student cohort. The agreement not only speaks to their individual cognitive strengths but also emphasizes a shared recognition of their collective proficiency in the realm of intrapersonal intelligence.
- 9.The teacher's agreement with a high level of linguistic intelligence is substantiated by their effective verbal communication, adeptness in written expression, a penchant for reading, sensitivity to linguistic nuances, and potential involvement in linguistic activities. These factors collectively contribute to a comprehensive demonstration of advanced linguistic intelligence within the teacher's skill set. The recognition and appreciation of linguistic intricacies play a pivotal role in creating a dynamic and enriching educational experience for students under the guidance of a linguistically intelligent educator.
- 10.The teacher's agreement with a high level of musical intelligence is supported by their ability to play a musical instrument, extensive knowledge of musical genres, incorporation of music into education, potential involvement in composition, and deliberate use of musical elements in the classroom. These facets collectively contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the teacher's advanced musical intelligence, highlighting a multifaceted engagement with the expressive and cognitive dimensions of music within both personal and educational contexts.
- 11.The teacher's agreement with a high level of logical-mathematical intelligence is substantiated by their proficiency in mathematical concepts, comfort with systematic problem-solving, potential involvement in advanced activities, effective communication of mathematical ideas, and the application of logical-mathematical skills beyond professional contexts. This comprehensive set of attributes supports the recognition of the teacher's advanced logical-mathematical intelligence, highlighting a multifaceted cognitive strength within the domain of abstract reasoning and quantitative problem-solving.
- 12.The teacher's agreement with a high level of spatial intelligence is supported by their enjoyment of drawing, potential engagement in spatial reasoning activities, use of

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spatial representations in teaching, and alignment with fields that emphasize spatial thinking. These facets collectively contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the teacher's advanced spatial intelligence, highlighting a multifaceted cognitive strength within the realm of visual-spatial perception and manipulation.

13. The teachers' agreement with a high level of bodily-kinesthetic intelligence is substantiated by their liking for dancing, potential engagement in physical activities or sports, an appreciation for performing arts, and the application of movement in teaching practices. These facets collectively contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the teachers' advanced bodily-kinesthetic intelligence, highlighting a multifaceted proficiency in physical and kinesthetic skills.
14. The teacher's agreement with a high level of interpersonal intelligence is substantiated by their positive relationships, conflict resolution skills, mentorship roles, and enjoyment of social events. These facets collectively contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the teacher's advanced interpersonal intelligence, highlighting a multifaceted proficiency in navigating and positively influencing social dynamics within both personal and professional spheres.
15. The teacher's agreement with a high level of intrapersonal intelligence is supported by their engagement in introspective practices, effective emotional regulation, goal-setting abilities, and a potential comfort in solitary activities. These facets collectively contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the teacher's advanced intrapersonal intelligence, highlighting their ability to navigate their internal world with self-awareness, emotional resilience, and a proactive approach to personal growth.
16. The assessment of linguistic intelligence based on age groups, gender, and grade levels demonstrates a consistent pattern with no statistically significant differences.
17. The analysis reveals that while age, educational attainment, and linguistic intelligence exhibit significant differences among mentor respondents, gender and years of service do not significantly influence linguistic intelligence scores.
18. The observed significant difference in the assessment of multiple intelligences between mentees and mentors emphasizes the need for a nuanced understanding of how individuals perceive their own intellectual capabilities.

Recommendations

1. Given the lack of significant differences in linguistic intelligence among mentees based on age, gender, and grade level, further investigation could explore other potential factors influencing linguistic intelligence. Additionally, examining how linguistic intelligence develops over time and identifying specific language-related skills that may vary among mentees could provide valuable insights.
2. The significant difference in linguistic intelligence based on educational attainment among mentors warrants deeper exploration. Researchers could investigate the specific linguistic skills that mentors with higher educational attainment attribute to their success. This understanding could inform educational strategies and mentorship programs aimed at enhancing linguistic intelligence.

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3. The observed significant difference in the assessment of multiple intelligences between mentees and mentors opens avenues for a more in-depth examination. Qualitative research methods, such as interviews or focus group discussions, could be employed to gain a richer understanding of the factors influencing self-perception of multiple intelligences. This qualitative data could complement the quantitative findings and provide a more comprehensive perspective.
4. Recognizing the differences in how mentees and mentors perceive their multiple intelligences, mentorship programs could be tailored to address individual needs. Mentorship initiatives could incorporate self-awareness and self-assessment components, allowing mentees and mentors to reflect on and articulate their strengths and areas for development across various intelligences.
5. Conducting longitudinal studies to track the development of multiple intelligences among both mentees and mentors could offer insights into how these abilities evolve over time. Examining the trajectories of linguistic, musical, logical-mathematical, spatial, bodily-kinesthetic, interpersonal, and intrapersonal intelligences could provide valuable information for educators and mentors aiming to support comprehensive intelligence development.
6. Ensuring that intelligence assessments consider diverse cultural backgrounds, experiences, and learning styles is crucial. Researchers could explore how cultural factors may influence the perception of intelligence, aiming for assessments that are more inclusive and representative of the mentee and mentor populations.
7. Recognizing the impact of educational attainment on linguistic intelligence among mentors, institutions could offer professional development opportunities that focus on enhancing specific linguistic skills. Workshops, training sessions, or mentorship programs that address language-related competencies could contribute to mentors' effectiveness in supporting mentees.

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